

cessda

KPI

**PERFORMANCE
INDICATORS**

**CESSDA
Key Performance
Indicators Report**

1st Collection

Author

Ivana Ilijasic Versic

Reviewers

Ron Dekker, CESSDA Main Office, Herve L'Hours, UKDS

Contributors

CESSDA Service Providers

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1. Introduction

The European Commission (EC), Member states (MS), Associated Countries (AC), and Funders (ministries or research councils) need to evaluate participation of countries in international organisations, and in particular research infrastructures, on a regular basis.

The EU Competitiveness Council recognised the priority to act on sustainability of Research Infrastructures (RIs) beyond 2020 and provide “sustainable and effective ecosystem for science and society”. The Conclusions of the meeting held on 28-29 May 2018¹ addressed the policy debate on research and innovation within the context of the next EU financial framework (2021 – 2027), particularly on “Accelerating knowledge circulation in the EU”.

Further, the document stated that for the long-term sustainability of Research Infrastructures, The Council²: «...Stresses the importance of human resources and training skills as key factors in the success for Research Infrastructures and ACKNOWLEDGES the need for Research Infrastructures to strengthen a service-driven approach; INVITES Member States and the Commission within the framework of ESFRI to develop a common approach for monitoring of their performance and INVITES the Pan-European Research Infrastructures, on a voluntary basis, to include it in their governance and explore options to support this through the use of Key Performance Indicators.»

In 2019, the EC installed a High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) and assigned the task of «assessing the effectiveness of the EU measures supporting the development of a well-balanced and competitive European Research Infrastructure system. The HLEG was also asked to assess the implementation of a representative group of RIs and their plans for ensuring long-term sustainability³».

The Report of the High-Level Expert Group to Assess the Progress of ESFRI and Other World Class Research Infrastructures Towards Implementation and Long-Term Sustainability⁴ was published in 2020. In part of the report dedicated to distributed RIs, CEESDA was praised as an established and fully functioning RI, however, the issue of sustainability and appropriate funding model was stressed.

1 Competitiveness Council, General Secretariat: Council conclusions on “Accelerating knowledge circulation in the EU”, 8940/1/18 REV1 RECH 183 COMPET 310, 29 May 2018

2 Ibidem, p.10-11

3 The Report of the High-Level Expert Group to Assess the Progress of ESFRI and Other World Class Research Infrastructures Towards Implementation and Long-Term Sustainability: *Supporting the Transformative Impact of Research Infrastructures on European Research*. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation Research and Innovation Infrastructures, 2020. Accessible at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/research_and_innovation/strategy_on_research_and_innovation/documents/ec_rtd_transformative-impact-ris-on-euro-research.pdf

4 Ibidem

2. Policy level requirements

2.1 ESFRI Monitoring Working Group

In response to the invitation of the Competitiveness Council, from May 2018, an ESFRI Monitoring Working Group (WG) was formed with the aim to develop a common approach across Research Infrastructures, and to monitor their performance based on Key Performance Indicators. The outcomes of the WG activities were presented during the ESFRI Meeting in mid-December 2019. A survey regarding the relevance of monitoring certain objectives for each RI was administered in late 2019. The relevance of the following objectives was examined:

- A. Scientific Excellence,
- B. Education and Training,
- C. Facilitating regional and transnational collaboration and activity in Europe,
- D. Innovation and knowledge transfer,
- E. Outreach to public and policy makers,
- F. Data,
- G. Support for Public Policies and Standards,
- H. International cooperation,
- I. Governance.

The table outlining relevance scores provided by CESSDA can be found in a separate Annex to this document. The survey resulted in 21 most relevant objectives, shared by responding pan-European RIs. The WG also developed a set of related KPIs to address those objectives (Table 1).

Table 1: ESFRI survey – most common RIs Objectives and related KPIs

Objective	KPIs
Achieving scientific excellence	1. Number of user requests for access 2. Number of users served 3. Number of publications 4. Percentage of top (10%) cited publications
Delivery of education and training	5. Number of MSc and PhD students using the RI 6. Training of people who are not RI staff
Enhancing collaboration in Europe	7. Number of Members of the RI from ESFRI countries 8. Share of users and publications per ESFRI member country
Facilitating economic activities	9. Share of users associated with industry and publications with industry 10. Income from commercial activities and the number of entities paying for service
Outreach to the public	11. Engagement achieved by direct contact 12. Outreach through media 13. Outreach via the RI's own web and social media

Objective	KPIs
Optimising data use	14. Number of publicly available data sets used externally
Provision of scientific advice	15. Participation by RIs in policy related activities 16. Citations in policy related publications
Facilitating international co-operation	17. Share of users and publications per non-ESFRI member country 18. International trainees 19. Number of members of the RI from non-ESFRI countries
Optimising management	20. Revenues 21. Extent of resources made available

2.1.1 Proposed methodology

The mandate of the ESFRI WG was to propose a common approach for the monitoring of RI performance. ESFRI acknowledged that indicators cannot be applied across all the RIs, due to many differences (in objectives, type, operations, etc.), therefore the RIs should use the KPIs that are suitable for them and that some adaptations to each specific RI would be needed.

To assure a high-quality monitoring system used by each of the RIs, ESFRI would:

- undertake evaluation of the quality of the monitoring system as part of its periodic review of the pan-European RIs,
- ask the RIs during the interviews to present the KPIs that they use, their reference sheets, and the values of the KPIs, keeping in mind that their purpose is to follow the development of a particular RI, not to compare RIs with each other,
- encourage the RIs to periodically collect their data.

The survey results also underlined the need to consider the context leading to refinement of some of the KPIs through consensus with funding bodies. Ideally, it should be an interdependent process of better understanding the KPIs and developing them further.

ESFRI assumed the responsibility for overseeing the implementation and monitoring of KPIs.

2.2 ERIC Forum response

The ERIC Forum Implementation project⁵ has been funded through the H2020, with a duration of 48 months. It started in January 2019 and will end in December 2022. It brings together 20 established European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) and 3 ERICs in preparation. The ERIC Forum is a collective initiative of currently 23 European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) and aspiring ERICs with the mission to «enhance collaboration and knowledge transfer between ERICs and provide them with a common voice for issues concerning ERICs as part of the European Research Area and the further development of the ERIC regulation». In response to the invitation of the Competitiveness Council from May 2018, and in line with tackling monitoring and evaluation of ERICs via project activities (WP4 on KPI development), ERIC Forum published a “Position Paper on the Development of KPIs for Research Infrastructures”⁶ in July 2019.

ERIC Forum positions regarding evaluation and monitoring of KPIs are summarised below:

- The ERIC Forum supports the development of a common understanding of KPIs and wants to actively contribute to the ongoing discussions.

5 <https://www.eric-forum.eu/about-the-eric-forum-implementation-project/>

6 <https://www.eric-forum.eu/2019/07/09/eric-forum-position-paper-on-the-development-of-kpis-for-research-infrastructures/>

- KPIs should be tailored to the specific objectives and mission of each ERIC.
- KPIs should only be used to benchmark an RI against its own performance and not to compare RIs.
- KPIs should comply with well-proven criteria for setting up indicators and measures.
- KPIs and indicators to measure socio-economic impact are not the same, even though a limited number of selected KPIs could be used to measure impact.

2.3 ESFRI conclusions and recommendations

As a result, and in cooperation with ERIC Forum, the final ESFRI report was published on 16 January 2020. Main conclusions:

1. KPIs can be implemented effectively if they are adapted to the specific character and context of individual RIs.
2. The proposed methodology requests that the RIs accompany the agreed KPIs with a context and develop their own narratives to better describe progress towards objectives.
3. Not all KPIs, or even all objectives, will be equally relevant to all RIs.
4. A Monitoring Implementation Group to be established by ESFRI:
 - to support the implementation and monitor the adoption and use of the KPIs,
 - to refine them through the experience gained through this process, and
 - to help establish best practice across European RIs and their stakeholders.
5. The KPIs for each RI are to be established in 2020, in a dialogue between the RIs, their boards/funders/ministries, the Strategic Working Groups (SWGs) of ESFRI addressing a specific domain (ESFRI SSH Strategic Group), and the Monitoring Implementation Group. The Group may also play the role of facilitator for the use of the KPIs at the time when the RI evaluation/assessment is carried out, either by ESFRI or by external agencies.

The following recommendations were shared:

- All KPIs should be aligned with the objectives of RIs and fulfil RACER criteria (Relevant, Accepted, Credible, Easy to monitor, Robust).
- Each KPI should be accompanied by a reference sheet that provides:
 - a definition,
 - data source(s),
 - method of calculation,
 - and other issues concerning calculation or applicability.

Although the report was mentioned several times in the coming period, there were no major updates to it, probably due to pandemic and imposed restrictions. However, the WG continued to exist and resumed its activities in mid-2021.

7 https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/ESFRI_WG_Monitoring_Report.pdf

3. CESSDA KPIs

3.1 Process

CESSDA discussions on evaluation and monitoring of research infrastructures started in early 2019 at its Service Providers' Forum (SPF) meeting. Particular attention was on tackling the RI landscape analysis and efforts by the EC in streamlining funding to clustering within scientific domains as the number of ESFRIs had been becoming too big to manage efficiently. In parallel, there was a clear incentive towards the ERIC Forum (via ERIC Forum Implementation project) to get more formalised and organised. The main concern at the time was the possibility of using the KPIs and sustainability of RIs' reports to develop a 'one size fits all' approach for monitoring.

CESSDA's General Assembly was informed about the evaluation and monitoring initiatives and discussions at its November meeting in 2019. The need for CESSDA to engage in developing its own KPIs followed a piloting role in the RI-PATHS H2020⁸ project on socio-economic impact and quality assessment, and partly because of its own management needs.

Throughout 2020 CESSDA Main Office (MO) in close collaboration with an ad hoc Working Group on KPIs development (members from 4 CESSDA Service Providers) and CESSDA Working Group Leaders (Training, Tools, Trust and Technical) addressed the final ESFRI report on monitoring and evaluation in the following manner:

1. The initial (wish) list of KPIs was drafted by the ad hoc WG, taking into account ESFRI proposed KPIs, existing CESSDA KPIs (functionality, capacity, user experience, impact), 'CESSDA in Numbers' exercise from 2018, discussions at the ERIC Forum, and CESSDA Strategic Plan 2018-2022.
2. This list was further refined through discussions between MO and CESSDA WG leaders. It was also decided that some of the KPIs would be used for internal monitoring, at least in initial collections, and some would be shared externally as aggregated measures.
3. Next, the list was presented at the SPF April 2020 meeting.
4. The list was again refined in terms of impact assessment and activity progress assessment via RI-PATHS pilot.
5. At the June GA, a framework for performance monitoring was presented and approved.
6. The draft KPIs' list was shared with the Service Providers via Basecamp on 26 June, with a deadline for responses set for 31 July. Detailed responses from several SPs were received by the end of July and in early August.
7. Updates of the draft KPIs list were done in the period of 10 August to 10 September, and they included:
 - shortening the initial list of 36 KPIs (18 internal, 18 public) to 20 (11 internal and 9 public) in the following way:
 - relevance of KPIs for the Consortium,
 - overlapping KPIs were combined or removed,
 - second round of edits done on descriptions of KPIs.
8. A second version of the KPI list was tested via a pilot data collection with selected Service Providers from 10 to 24 September. 7 SPs were contacted (based on regional aspect, organisational type, maturity, etc.), 5 agreed to participate: ADP, FORS, FSD, So.Da.Net, SND.
9. Further consultations followed the SPF October meeting (from 14 October to 6 November).

8 <https://ri-paths-tool.eu/en>

10. Updates of the 2nd version were based on the pilots' results and final comments by SPs.
11. The 3rd and final update of the KPIs' list was done in early November. It consisted of 12 KPIs: 6 internal and 6 public.
12. The final list of CESSDA KPIs was adopted by the GA on 24 November 2020.

It was concluded at the GA and later repeated at the spring SPF in 2021, as an intro to the collection process, that selection and definitions of indicators, the exact requirements from ESFRI, and the exact use of the information will evolve over time. This will be addressed in the first half of Agenda 2021-24 funding programme and in cooperation with all Service Providers. The initial degree of variability is acceptable, but at this point, CESSDA must prioritise information availability. The work to standardise and ensure comparability of these metrics will be done periodically. Revision of the current list of KPIs should be done in the second half of 2022.

3.2 Collection

Initial instructions and the collection timeline were announced at the 16th SPF meeting (April 2021). The first collection of CESSDA KPIs (for 2020) started on 20 May 2021, with a deadline of 20 June 2021. The final input was received in mid-August delaying the planned analysis and coordination with Trust Task activities in CESSDA Agenda 21-22.

All CESSDA Service Providers received the necessary collection information (i.e., links and supporting documents) via Basecamp platform created specifically for Directors.

Input was collected via a Google form containing the following parts:

- general part (timestamp, CESSDA Service Provider providing information, person providing information on behalf of the Service Provider, position of respondent within the organisation, and her/his email address),
- each of 12 CESSDA Key Performance Indicators had a certain number of questions covering sub-areas of interest requiring input, along with a commenting possibility.

Preliminary results were presented at the 17th SPF meeting in October 2021, followed by discussion and further clarifications at the CESSDA KPI workshop in mid-November, finally feeding into the report presented to the CESSDA GA in late November 2021.

4. Results per area and CESSDA KPIs (public)

4.1 Achieving Scientific Excellence

KPI no.1: Number of users

I01 Achieving Scientific Excellence - KPI no.1: Number of users

1. Total number of visitors across all externally facing products (website, tools, Nesstar, etc.).
2. Total number of registered users.
3. Total number of access requests per 'study' (or primary digital object).

Description: In seeking to identify an overall level of engagement through different measures we would like to consolidate three indicative numbers (accepting that local collection practice may vary) on total visitors across all externally facing products, total number of registered users and total number of access requests per 'study'. To be collected per SP but presented externally as an aggregated figure.

The following information was collected across CESSDA consortium: total number of visitors across all externally facing products (website, tools, Nesstar, etc.) summed up to almost 10 million (9 716 739) visitors, with around 300 thousand (287 811) of registered users and more than 350 thousands of access requests per 'study' or primary digital object (362 479).

It is worth noting that ca. 14% of CESSDA Service Providers couldn't provide any input due to the fact they didn't (at that point of their development) provide listed services and therefore couldn't report on users.

Around 30% of Service Providers provided partial information across questions due to various reasons (don't have direct access to registered users; impossible to count exact number of unique visitors; web and online statistics not updated; ongoing implementation of services; tracking just certain type of numbers; tracking only website visits; not tracking registered users; don't have registered users; data currently not available, i.e., registrations valid for academic year).

Final group of Service Providers were the ones that had elaborate systems of users' counting and provided all needed information.

One additional comment pointed to the direction of better formulation of the third question (total number of access requests per 'study' or primary digital object). One of the ways to define it is counting active requests resulting in a data delivery for restricted data sets in a particular period, that require an action from staff (most files can be downloaded directly or after login). This presents a small subset from the total amount of downloads or accesses to data.

Also, some Service Providers understood 'registered users' as 'active registered users' (i.e., users registered and having used services in 2020).

Given different practices and possibilities within the consortium to count the number of visitors, users, and access requests, further clarifications regarding this KPI are needed.

4.2 Delivery of Education and Training

KPI no.2: Number of training events and participants in training

I02 Delivery of Education and Training - KPI no.2: Number of training events and participants in training

1. Number of training/education events.
2. Number of training /education events' attendees.
3. Number of references to CESSDA in training/education at events.

Description: This metric is intended to capture the number of events and every participant at every event fully or partially providing training or education (that is not funded by a contribution from CESSDA) that an SP is involved in. It also seeks to capture the level of CESSDA promotion. To be collected per SP but presented externally as an aggregated figure.

According to collected information, a total of 467 training and/or educational events were either organised or attended (in an active role) by CESSDA Service Providers, and outside of the CESSDA funding programmes. Those events were attended by more than 10.000 people. Ideally, if mentioned every time, CESSDA would reach a significant number of people.

The number of references to CESSDA also revealed various results.

Out of 22 Service Providers organising or participating in training or educational events, 7 (or roughly 20%) didn't mention CESSDA on any occasion. Reasons are different, spanning from not being part of any event, thus unable to spread the word on CESSDA and reach out to participants, over some occasionally/irregularly mentioning CESSDA (ca. 50%), to a number of SPs (around 30%) who took every opportunity to mention CESSDA at external events they were participating in.

It should be taken into account that spreading the word about CESSDA needs to be meaningful and within the context of an event. In that sense, it is advisable to discuss and promote CESSDA products (DMEG, CDC, Dataverse/Kuha, data protection and DDI events...) whenever possible for SPs, especially in events based on existing collaborations, and where the content of the event is appropriate and beneficial to CESSDA activities and outputs.

Additional comments by some of the SPs addressed the challenges in 2020 for participation in events i.e., overall number of training and educational events was lower than usual due to COVID-19 restrictions. It was also mentioned that although some SPs didn't track references to CESSDA during training events, mentioning was assumed.

As a general action, it was suggested to offer a sentence for the last and/or first page of a presentation that references CESSDA. One of SPs often uses the following or a similar sentence in articles, marketing material and in email communication: "(SP name) is the (country) representative (or a service provider) in the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA ERIC)". One slide should be prepared every December and included in presentations by SPs in the following year.

4.3 Outreach to the public

KPI no.4: Number of presentations at conferences and events

104 Outreach to the public - KPI no.4: Number of presentations at conferences and events

1. Total number of events.
2. Number of events which reference CESSDA in any way.

Description: To be collected per SP but presented externally as an aggregated figure. This metric is intended to capture the number of events (not funded by a contribution from CESSDA) that an SP presents at. This could be any event which is not day to day administration or project business e.g., conferences, invited keynotes for research communities, to national or European bodies, and policy makers. It also seeks to capture the level of CESSDA promotion.

This indicator excludes previously collected information on training and educational events. It covers a more strategic level of communication to CESSDA stakeholders. Although quite similar to the previous KPI, it deals with a slightly different level of CESSDA promotion.

Service Providers reported a total of 440 events where they presented their work, and CESSDA was mentioned in a total of 76 occasions. 20% of SPs referenced CESSDA in each of their presentations at attended events. Around 30% mentioned CESSDA in the majority of their presentations, and 50% didn't mention CESSDA at all.

However, the comments section offered some clarity on provided information: i.e., numbers were likely to be somewhat underestimated due to the lack of entries by staff in operational databases. In addition, some SPs didn't track the number of references to CESSDA, but usually refer to it in all presentations, and some SPs track exclusively scientific conferences' presentations from researchers of the data archive, which consequently leads to much lower numbers reported.

4.4 Optimising Data Use

KPI no.5: Number of studies

105 Optimising Data Use - KPI no.5: Number of studies

1. A brief description of the kinds of objects/studies/datasets SP has and how they are changed and versioned over time.
2. The number of 'Studies' in total by local definition.
3. What is the local definition of 'a study'?

Description: Tracking the total number of studies available by a SP, including a brief description of the kinds of objects/studies/datasets and how they are changed and versioned over time, based on local definitions.

Given the variety of local definitions, provided information (at that point) couldn't be aggregated in meaningful information on the level of the whole consortium. However, certain categories of answers could have been drawn, based on explanations and additional comments provided by participating SPs.

16 out of 22 Service Providers (or around 70%) describe a study as 'a unit consisting of one or several dataset and related documentation' or a variation of that description. Assuming that definition of a study, it could be

concluded with some caution that CESSDA as a whole has around 32.000 studies exposed through its archives. Remaining SPs either didn't have any data yet (1 SP) or saw the term 'study' as equivalent to 'dataset'. A table with descriptions and local definitions is provided as a separate Annex to this document.

KPI no.6: Number of new studies

I06 Optimising Data Use - KPI no.6: Number of new studies

1. Number of completely new studies arriving in the archive.
2. Number of existing studies that have been updated with newly deposited content of any kind.

Description: Tracking the number of new studies added per year or updated existing studies (based on local definitions as above, so again to be taken with caution).

When it comes to completely new studies added to the archives' collections, the numbers varied:

- 0-10 for ca. 30 % of SPs
- 11-100 for ca. 40% of SPs
- 101-700 for ca. 30% of SPs

Same happened with the number of existing studies updated with newly deposited content of any kind:

- 0-10 for ca. 86% of SPs
- 11-100 for 10% of SPs
- 101-200 for 4% of SPs

According to explanations offered by the respondents, there were several reasons:

- For some SPs existing studies are rarely updated with newly deposited content. Changes to existing data are often due to added anonymisation measures, the release of embargoed variables, or correction of errors.
- Some SPs don't distinguish between newly deposited content and updates (i.e., updated dataset (due to typos or data protection issues), it means a version upgrade, not newly deposited content. Therefore, it cannot be tracked easily).
- Additional reasons could be the maturity of the archive, internal capacity of processing, procedures, policy, and legislation related to research work, etc.

For both KPI05 and KPI06 further clarifications are needed.

4.5 Optimising Management

KPI no.7: Number of staff per SP (FTE)

I07 Optimising Management - KPI no.7: Number of staff per SP (FTE)

1. Total number of staff FTE per SP.

Description: Total number of staff per SP, and related only to staff at SPs, not their legal entities, expressed as Full Time Equivalent (FTE).

Reported numbers across SPs varied due to the size of the institution, its structure, maturity, scope of work, (...), to name a few. The following categories based on the number of staff per SP (FTE) were observed:

- 1-10 FET for ca. 60% SPs
- 11-100 for ca. 36% of SPs
- 101-200 for ca. 4% of SPs

In total, around full-time 590 staff positions (in FTEs) are reported over all CESSDA SPs. Although more than half SPs have less than 10 FTEs engaged in core business, it could depend on the size, maturity, scope of work and other variables not reported here.

Comments by SPs revealed in more detail what categories of staff were included in the numbers:

- administrative support and IT personnel included for some SPs, with students and IT as external collaborators
- mixture of permanent and temporary (fixed term) employees
- mixture of full time and part-time employees

In addition, some SPs emphasised their dependence on funding from the ministry or a research council for adding more staff.

5. Results per area and CESSDA KPIs (internal)

5.1 Enhancing Collaboration in Europe/Facilitation of international collaboration

KPI no.3: Number of collaborative projects outside of RI (CESSDA)

I03 Enhancing Collaboration in Europe/Facilitation international collaboration - KPI no.3: Number of collaborative projects outside of RI (CESSDA)

1. Number of EU and/or other projects SP is participating in outside of CESSDA.

Description: Tracking the number of EU and other projects SP is participating in outside of CESSDA (e.g., as part of other research infrastructures).

This indicator is part of the wider ESFRI area of 'Enhancing Collaboration in Europe/Facilitation international collaboration'. It shows engagement of CESSDA Service Providers in other national and international initiatives, thus indicating the level of impact CESSDA could potentially have on national and international level indirectly through its SPs. However, given some misunderstandings during the collection process, further clarifications regarding this KPI are needed.

5.2 Optimising Management

KPI no.8: Annual Budget per SP

I08 Optimising Management - KPI no.8: Annual Budget per SP

1. Amount of national funding per SP (in EUR).

Description: Amount of national funding per SP (in EUR); refers to funding received by a SP per year from the Research Council/Ministry or any national funding body for its usual/main operations. If not allocated directly to SP, it can be part of funding provided to a legal entity (e.g., University of Tampere, that CESSDA's SP, FSD, belongs to).

According to GERD⁹ (gross domestic expenditure on R&D, more detail provided in separate Annex), countries are divided into 4 categories:

- countries with investment in R&D lower than 1% of GDP,
- countries with investment in R&D between 1-2% of GDP,
- countries with investment in R&D more than 2% of GDP,
- countries with investment in R&D more than 3% of GDP.

9 GERD: The indicator measures gross domestic expenditure on R&D (GERD) as a percentage of the gross domestic product (GDP). "Research and experimental development (R&D) comprise creative work undertaken on a systematic basis in order to increase the stock of knowledge, including knowledge of man, culture and society and the use of this stock of knowledge to devise new applications" (Frascati Manual, 2002 edition, § 63)

Provided information again suggested several categories of CESSDA SPs based on the amounts received nationally for core activities:

- 0-10.000 EUR for 5 SPs (ca. 23%) in this category, 2 SPs receiving 0 EUR in terms of national funding (still waiting for a funding contract from the ministry/RC even after being in CESSDA for several years),
- 10.001-50.000 EUR for 1 SP (ca. 5%),
- 50.001-100.000 EUR for 4 SPs (ca. 18%),
- 100.001-500.000 EUR for 4 SPs (ca. 18%),
- 1.000.000-3.000.000 EUR for 4 SPs (ca. 18%),
- >3.000.000 EUR for 4 SPs (ca. 18%).

Out of 4 countries with more than 3% of GDP devoted to R&D, only one gives aligned proportional support further to its SP.

From 5 countries that initially reported national financing lower than 10 thousand EUR per year, when comparing GERD and actual investments in SPs as the percentage of GDP, it is revealed that 1 additional SP belongs in that category.

However, the majority of SPs gets national support aligned with the country's category of GERD.

Provided input also suggested that, for the vast majority of SPs, funding is provided by the ministry or research councils.

KPI no.9: Engagement in CESSDA activities (FTE)

109 Optimising Management - KPI no.9: Engagement in CESSDA activities (FTE)

1. Number of staff FTE assigned and working on CESSDA activities.

Description: Number of staff assigned and working on CESSDA activities. Relates to additional engagement on the side of the SP, not part of usual RI funding channels (fees, or participation in internal and EC projects run by CESSDA), expressed as FTE (Full Time Equivalent).

The provided input revealed that a total of around 41 full-time positions (expressed as FTE) across the consortium is assigned to work on CESSDA activities and provided for by national resources. Again, several categories of engagement were revealed:

- 0-1 FTE for 9 SPs (ca. 41%): 3 SPs reporting 0 FTE devoted to CESSDA activities and 1 reporting N/A,
- 1-2 FTEs for 3 SPs (ca. 14%),
- 2-5 FTEs for 9 SPs (ca. 41%),
- 1 with 11 FTEs reported (ca. 4%).

However, as expressed in comments, the reasons and accounting of allocated contributions to CESSDA is based on different reasoning: as a project work, part of qualitative assessment, bonus based on delivery, in-kind contribution, etc.

There could be a slight misunderstanding for some of the SPs, since being assigned and working on CESSDA activities also means all the in-kind contributions for participation at the SPF and GA meetings, participation in Working Groups, contributing to ad-hoc activities (COVID-19 webpage, KPIs development), preparation for connections to CDC, etc. It is also not an equivalent to archive work. Further clarifications regarding this KPI are needed.

KPI no.10: Annual budget for participation in CESSDA

I010 Optimising Management - KPI no.10: Annual budget for participation in CESSDA

1. Amount of national funding awarded per SP for CESSDA activities (in EUR).

Description: Amount of national funding awarded to SP directly by national authorities for CESSDA activities (in EUR).

In total, SPs reported 2.208.118 EUR awarded for CESSDA activities by national authorities. However, reasoning again varies; funds are allocated to CESSDA fees and travel arrangements for some SPs; some receive it as a direct support from their national funders, or use other funds not related specifically to CESSDA. Finally, some SPs (ca. 23%) don't get additional national funding for participation in CESSDA.

5.3 Readiness for EOSC (including FAIR)

KPI no.11: Compliance to FAIR principles

I011 Readiness for EOSC (including FAIR) - KPI no.11: Compliance to FAIR principles

1. How many datasets/studies have been evaluated and with what tools (e.g. FAIR metrics; <https://www.fairsfair.eu/f-uji-automated-fair-data-assessment-tool>. <https://www.fairsfair.eu/fair-aware>)

Description: Repositories' ability to enable compliance with FAIR principles, e.g., FAIR metrics (FAIR Maturity Evaluation Service) or EOSCNordic or FAIRsFAIR (in %). The tools only measure individual objects, although that can be generalised to the containing repository to some extent. As a first step, each SP can select an object of their choice to measure FAIRness.

This indicator represents a commitment to monitoring and complying with FAIR Principles. Initially MO wants to be able to demonstrate to ESFRI/EOSC an engagement with enabling FAIR data. This will involve testing and evaluation of the evolving indicators and metrics through the tools currently being developed. Initially we will seek to identify how many datasets/studies have been evaluated and with what tools.

→ [F-UJI Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool](#)

→ [FAIR-AWARE](#)

Only 7 out of 22 SPs (ca. 32%) provided answers to this KPI.

Some of the SPs had not yet conducted any FAIR evaluations of their datasets at the time of collection. Some secured compliance with the principles only through the processes based on their preservation policy and CESSDA recommendations. Some performed assessment based on the data portals rather than single data sets. One SP used the FAIR Implementation Profiles for a FAIR-SWOT Analysis to assess FAIRness of its data catalogue and the metadata disseminated through the catalogue. Any systematic use of suggested tools needs to be checked with experts internally.

Some of the SPs had assessed their data via the suggested tools, either individually, or being part of the EOSC-NORDIC project.

Provided comments suggested that this KPI might need some time to be fully adopted throughout the consortium, and their usage should be re-considered until the next revision of the KPI list. Further clarifications regarding this KPI are needed.

KPI no.12: Number of operational systems meeting the CESSDA criteria for a TRL-8 production service

I012 Readiness for EOSC (including FAIR) - KPI no.12: Number of operational systems that meet the CESSDA criteria for a TRL-8 production service

1. Total number of operational systems at TRL8; manual counting - according to the CESSDA Quality guidelines (approved by TWG May 2020).

Description: Manual counting, i.e., technical systems that are publicly accessible online, either anonymously or via some form of authentication. Information to be provided by each SPs, even though the criteria are CESSDA-specific. Although currently limited to technical services, having this number can offer an indicator for how many technical services SPs are offering and at what maturity.

Provided answers can be summarized in several categories:

- Only 6 SPs (or ca. 27%) provided an answer to the question related to KPI12. For 5 of them, the number of operational systems reported varies between 1 and 5, and one SP reported the high number of 45 operational systems that meet the CESSDA criteria for a TRL-8 production service. A comment regarding uncertainty whether some systems may adhere to TRL7 or TRL8 was also shared within this group.
- 9 SPs (or ca. 41%) marked non-applicable (N/A) as their answer, mostly due to no systems assessed according to CESSDA criteria or no assessment done at all. Some also reported other departments dealing with technical developments, thus not being able to report on actual status.
- 7 SPs (or ca. 32%) put zero as their answer, connected to no operational tools at that level

Given uncertainties and low number of SPs able to provide answers, further clarifications regarding this KPI are needed.

6. Recommendations and next steps

6.1 CESSDA

For CESSDA, definition and collection of KPIs is the first step towards systematic internal monitoring and evaluation of CESSDA performance, as well as timely response to external requirements for sustainability of operations (ESFRI, EC), internal benchmarking and alignment with peer RIs (in SSH domain) and other scientific clusters (EOSC).

As recommended by ESFRI, the monitoring process evolves over time, and includes joint understanding of indicators and their measure on all levels of organisational structure. The initial development of CESSDA KPIs took almost 2 years of preparations and wide consultations throughout different bodies of the Consortium.

However, the process is far from over; preliminary results in this report need to be thoroughly discussed at the upcoming 17th SPF meeting, with the group of respondents and Trust Working Group representatives in a dedicated workshop after the SPF, before the final report on 2020 CESSDA KPIs can be submitted to the General Assembly.

After the first collection there were key questions that needed to be answered and clarified in order to offer more understanding of collected data:

- identify areas where majority of SP can/cannot offer answers at this moment, and why,
- revise current definitions of some KPIs and clarify further to avoid misunderstandings,
- discuss level of granularity for some KPIs vs. big overall numbers to demonstrate impact; presentation in wider context,
- discuss observed trends and assess the need for further or more complex analyses,
- discuss how to make internal process (methodology, collection, understanding) better
- discuss the evolution of KPIs over time,
- revise the dissemination level of some of KPIs (public vs. internal KPIs) keeping in mind wider context and interpretation of information (to funders, EC, etc.).

CESSDA is ready to meet the requirements set by the European Competitiveness Council in 2018: it developed KPIs in line with its core business, strategy, structure, funders requirements and incoming external demands (i.e., EOSC).

The design of CESSDA KPIs will evolve over time, as stated previously. The first review of current KPIs is set for the 2nd part of 2022 and needs to be aligned with the updated CESSDA Strategy (currently in the review process), further definition of internal development directions set out in Consolidated Roadmap and Agenda 21-24, and finalisation of several EC funded projects, especially SSHOC.

The evaluations by ESFRI Monitoring WG will start in early 2022 with Landmarks and are planned to be finished by 2024. Feedback will be considered and implemented, which may again require changes to the KPIs at that point.

6.2 ESFRI

On the policy level, the EC Stakeholder workshop held on 13 and 14 September 2021 shed some more light on expectations from the RIs (ERICs in particular) and revealed further efforts in terms of their monitoring and evaluation. ESFRI representatives once again stressed the need to monitor the performance of Landmarks, how they feed into ERA priorities, and how they interconnect.

There is a clear need for periodic assessment of Landmarks and their performance. Until now, ESFRI didn't carry out any further assessment of the Landmarks, because there was no instrument to measure and ensure their continued relevance.

However, ESFRI has now developed a Monitoring approach for Landmarks based on a principle of self-assessment:

- The concept methodology is fully compliant with the EU Council conclusions from May 2018.
- It is based on combined use of KPIs developed by ESFRI and evaluation of the scientific and implementation case for each Landmark.
- It was presented and approved at the ESFRI Forum in September 2021.
- The concept was expected to be fully developed by the end of 2021.

ESFRI is planning to start the evaluation of RIs in early 2022 and to conclude the first round of evaluation in 2024 for all operational Landmarks. The process will be repeated on a 5-year term.

The 1st KPI collection took place in 2021, for data related to 2020.

The CESSDA KPIs will be monitored and collected on a yearly basis.

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